

A Cross-Sectional Study of Pulmonary Function Tests in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract:

Background: Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder which can lead to multiorgan complications, broadly divided into microvascular and macrovascular complications. The estimates in 2019 showed that 77 million individuals had diabetes in India, which is expected to rise to over 134 million by 2045. Lungs are a potential target organ for diabetic microvascular complications and so this study was undertaken to see the impairment of pulmonary functions using spirometry in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Aims and Objectives: The study was undertaken to analyze the pulmonary function parameters in type II diabetic patients and compare them with age and gender matched healthy subjects. Correlation between forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV₁) in diabetic patients with duration of the disease was also analyzed.

Materials and Methods: Pulmonary function tests (PFTs) were recorded in 100 type 2 diabetic patients and 100 normal healthy controls aged between 30 - 60 years by using Medspiror. The PFTs analysed statistically were – Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) and Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV₁) to find the correlation between diabetics and non - diabetics. Glycemic status (FBS & PPBS) of subjects were determined by Glucose oxidase & peroxidase methods. PFTs of diabetic patients and controls were compared by applying Student's unpaired t test. Associations between FVC and FEV₁ and duration of illness in diabetic patients were analyzed by applying Pearson's coefficient.

Results: The mean FVC in the total diabetic group is 2.25±0.64 L which is lower than that of the total non-diabetic control group (2.64±0.81L) and the decreased value in the total diabetic control group is very highly significant (p<0.001). The mean FEV₁ in the total diabetic group is 1.72 ± 0.51 L and it is significantly lower than that of the total non-diabetic control group which is 2.14 ± 0.59 (p<0.001). There is negative correlation between the FVC as well as FEV₁ with the duration of disease among the total diabetic group and this is statistically not significant.

Conclusion: Lung function tests are likely to be impaired in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Pulmonary Function Tests.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is characterised by disordered metabolism and inappropriate hyperglycaemia due to either a deficiency of insulin secretion or to a combination of insulin resistance and inadequate insulin secretion to compensate. A number of pathological changes involve the small and large blood vessels, cranial and peripheral nerves, skin and eyes resulting in hypertension, renal failure, blindness, neuropathy, myocardial infarction and cerebrovascular accidents. Chronic hyperglycemia in diabetes results in the formation of advanced glycation end products (AGE). This induces pro-inflammatory changes and cross-linking of collagen in the endothelial basement membrane which leads

to vascular complications.[1] The World Health Organization estimates that more than 180 million people worldwide have diabetes, and by 2030 it is expected that this number will have doubled.[2] There is an alarming increase in the incidence and prevalence of diabetes mellitus (DM) in Asian Indians.[3] Routine investigations are essential in persons suffering from diabetes mellitus to monitor the control of the disease as well as evaluate the complications. Lungs, being a highly perfused vital organ, possess extensive microvasculature which remains unexplored, and lung involvement results in cardiovascular morbidities. These may be ignored due to the absence of early clinical signs[4].Some

studies have reported normal lung function tests in person suffering from diabetes mellitus but other studies have reported abnormal respiratory parameters. The impact in the lung functions may be probably influenced by duration of the disease and the status of glycaemic control. Effects of pulmonary diabetic micro-angiopathy is not so evident probably because of the large pulmonary reserve and thus the pulmonary complications are less marked in persons suffering from diabetes mellitus. Few studies are conducted concerning these the relationship between DM and pulmonary function tests (PFTs) and these studies are important epidemiologically and clinically.

Hypothesis: PFTs are affected in persons suffering from DM in Indian population and the changes may correlate to the duration of the disease.

Objectives:

1. To evaluate the pulmonary function parameters of an individual with diabetes mellitus
2. To compare the pulmonary function parameters in diabetic patients and with age and gender matched healthy subjects
3. To correlate the pulmonary function parameters with duration of diabetes mellitus.

Material and Methods

The study was carried out in Assam Medical College, Dibrugarh, Assam. The Institutional Ethics Committee approved the study protocol. . Hundred diagnosed cases of diabetic mellitus aged 30 to 60 yrs with duration more than 6 months who were on treatment were randomly selected from the Medicine Outpatient Department. Hundred healthy (age and gender matched) control were included in this study. Ventilatory functions were measured by Medspiror. Glycemic status (FBS & PPBS) of subjects were determined by Glucose oxidase & peroxidase methods.

Inclusion criteria of the cases:

1. Diagnosed cases of diabetes mellitus aged between 30 -60 with duration of disease for at least 6 months and on treatment.
2. Diabetics who has no history of lower respiratory tract illness and with symptoms related to respiratory illness (nasal itching and congestion, running nose, dry throat, hoarseness, epistaxis, sneezing, pain suggestive of sinusitis, cough, expectoration and dyspnea) at the time of examination.

Inclusion criteria of the controls: Healthy age and gender matched non-diabetic individuals.

Exclusion criteria both cases and controls:

1. Present or past history of respiratory disease that might affect pulmonary function such as asthma, COPD, tuberculosis, bronchiectasis, interstitial lung disease.
2. History of occupational exposure to any substances that could affect lung function.
3. Individual with current upper or lower respiratory infection.
4. Individual with unacceptable spirometric technique.
5. Individual with gross abnormalities of vertebral column or thoracic case.
6. Individuals with neuromuscular disease, malignancy, cardiopulmonary disease
7. Individual with history of major abdominal or thoracic surgery.

Informed written consent was taken from patients as well as from controls. A questionnaire that contained a detailed personal and medical history was taken from the cases as well as controls. PFTs of the patients was done by trained personnel. The controls and patients performed spirometry three times at the interval of 15 minutes and the best of the three was taken into account. Parameters recorded were – forced vital capacity (FVC) in liters, forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1), FEV1/FVC in percentage (%), forced expiratory flow during 25% of FVC (FEF25), forced expiratory flow during 50% of FVC (FEF50), forced expiratory flow during 75% of FVC (FEF75), forced expiratory flow during 25-75% of FVC (FEF25-75), forced expiratory flow during 0.2-1.2 liters of FVC (FEF0.2-1.2), and peak expiratory flow rate (PEFR).

Measurement of glycemic control: Nearly 2 mL of venous blood was from all diabetic patients and healthy controls with aseptic precautions. Glycemic status was determined by recording fasting blood sugar (FBS) and postprandial blood sugar (PPBS) by Glucose oxidase & peroxidase methods.

Results and Observation

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 patients with diabetes mellitus and 100 age and gender matched healthy non-diabetic individuals with normal blood glucose level, including both males and females without any respiratory disease. The observations made was noted and after the completion of the study the data was organized using Microsoft Office Excel 2007. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson's correlation coefficient were calculated for relevant groups as needed. 'p' values for inter group comparison were calculated using 'independent sample t - test' (two tailed, unequal variance) in SPSS – 16. Regression analysis was done to assess the association of diabetes mellitus with blood sugar and duration of disease.

Table 1: Demographic Parameters and Blood sugar level of the total study population

Parameters	Diabetic case(n=100)		Non-diabetic control(n=100)		P value
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Age (years)	50.36	8.38	48.53	7.07	>0.05
Height(cm)	157.38	8.35	158.68	7.53	>0.05
Weight(kg)	60.38	11.05	62.57	9.99	>0.05
BMI(kg/ m ²)	24.35	3.87	24.79	3.19	>0.05
FBS (mg/dl)/	204.13	78.40	95.49	10.57	<0.001
PPBS (mg/dl)	281.58	96.48	128.07	5.59	<0.001

Table 2: Demographic Parameters and Blood sugar level in males and females

Parameters	Male				P value	Female				P value
	Diabetic		Nondiabetic			Diabetic female		Nondiabetic		
	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD		Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD	
Age (yrs)	51.3	8.23	50.07	7.52	>.05	49.54	8.45	47.91	6.79	>.05
Ht(cm)	163.66	7.26	164.61	6.12	>.05	152.45	5.29	153.95	4.61	>.05
Wt (kg)	61.45	12.21	66.89	9.72	>.05	59.27	8.98	59.27	9.16	>.05
BMI kg/m ²	22.79	3.57	24.62	2.87	<.01	25.48	3.54	24.98	3.53	>.05
FBS (mg/dl)	208.11	87.39	94.09	11.97	<0.001	201	71.21	96.59	9.29	<0.001
PPBS(mg/dl)	294.41	102.61	126.48	5.48	<0.001	271.50	91.04	129.32	5.40	<0.001

Very highly significant difference of both fasting blood glucose and postprandial blood glucose level is seen between all diabetic and non-diabetic groups but no significant difference of those is present between diabetic males and diabetic females.

Table 3: Spirometric results in the study population

	Parameters	Diabetic case group (n=100)		Non-diabetic control group (n=100)		P value
		Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	
Total	FVC (L)	2.25	0.64	2.64	0.81	< 0.001
	FEV ₁ (L)	1.72	0.51	2.14	0.59	< 0.001
	FEV ₁ %	77.69	11.64	81.14	9.96	<0.05
Male	FVC (L)	2.65	0.54	3.17	0.67	< 0.001
	FEV ₁ (L)	2.01	0.5	2.55	0.6	< 0.001
	FEV ₁ %	76.35	9.9	80.89	9.03	<0.05
Female	FVC (L)	1.93	0.53	2.23	0.64	<0.01
	FEV ₁ (L)	1.50	0.40	1.83	0.34	<0.001
	FEV ₁ %	78.83	12.95	81.54	10.27	>0.05

The FVC in the total diabetic group is lower than that of the total non-diabetic control group which is very highly significant ($p < 0.001$). The mean FEV₁ and FEV₁ % in the total diabetic group is significantly lower than that of the total non-diabetic

control group. FVC and FEV₁ values are lower in diabetic males than non-diabetic males which is very highly significant ($p < 0.001$). There is significantly lower FVC and FEV₁ values ($p < 0.01$) in the diabetic females than non-diabetic females.

Figure 1

Fig. 1 (A, B, C) shows regression analysis of FVC, FEV₁ and FEV₁ % against FBS among the total diabetic group. There is insignificant negative correlation between FVC ($r = -0.11, p > 0.05$), FEV₁ ($r = -0.08, p > 0.05$) and FEV₁ % ($r = 0.11, P > 0.05$) of the total diabetic group and FBS as shown in Fig 1

Figure 2

Fig. 2 (A,B,C) - Regression analysis for FVC, FEV₁ and FEV₁ % against PPBS among the total diabetic group. There is no significant correlation of FVC (r = 0.07, p> 0.05), FEV₁ (r = 0.07, p> 0.05), FEV₁ % and PPBS among the diabetic cases in this study as shown in Fig 2.

Table 4: Duration of Diabetes in Years

Groups	Number of Cases	Disease Duration (Years)		Minimum (Years)	Maximum (Years)
		Mean	± SD		
Total	100	6.66	4.67	0.5	20
Male	44	6.11	4.09	0.5	18
Female	56	7.09	5.07	0.5	20

Table 5: Distribution of Cases According to Duration of DM

Groups	Number	%	Age (Years)		Duration of disease (Years)	
			Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD
0.5 yr- ≤ 5 yrs	47	47	46.85	8.3	2.81	1.65
>5yrs < 10	26	26	50.58	7.77	7.15	1.12
≥ 10 yrs	27	27	55.3	6.57	12.89	3.12

Figure 3:

Fig. 3(A, B, C) shows regression analyses for FVC, FEV₁ and FEV₁ % against duration of disease among the total diabetic group.

There is negative correlation between the FVC (r = - 0.16, p > 0.05), FEV₁ (r = - 0.13, p > 0.05) and insignificant correlation between FEV₁ % and duration of disease among the total diabetic group but this is statistically not significant as shown in Fig. 3.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to compare the pulmonary function tests of type 2 diabetes mellitus with healthy age and gender matched controls and also to analyze the correlation between the lung function parameters and duration of diabetes mellitus.

Our study shows a significant impairment in pulmonary functions in diabetic persons. There is a significant reduction in FVC and FEV₁ in diabetics when compared to matched controls.

Some other studies have also shown similar results. Davis et al.[5] conducted a large community-based study in Western Australia in type 2 diabetic patients and demonstrated that VC, FVC, FEV₁, and PEF were decreased in type 2 diabetic patients. They also suggested that the reduced lung volumes and airflow limitation are likely to be chronic complications of type 2 diabetes. Earl S. Ford et al (2004) [6] found that FEV₁ is significantly and inversely associated with the incidence of diabetes. D. A. Lawlor et al (2004) [7], Oritiz-Aguirre AR et al (2006) [8] also noted the same.

In the present study, the FEV₁ % in the total diabetic group is 3.45% lower than that of the total non-diabetic control group and this decrease is significant ($p < 0.05$). The corresponding decrease in the diabetic males and diabetic females are 4.54% and 2.71% respectively. The decrease in diabetic males is significant ($p < 0.05$) while that in diabetic females is insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Sreeja C. K. et al (2003)[9], Meta-analysis by Bram van den Borst et al (2010)[10], Anand R. Dharwadkar et al (2011)[11], B A Kolawole et al (2012)[12] observed a significant reduction of FEV₁/FVC% in DM.

The present study shows no significant correlation between lung function tests and duration of diabetes mellitus. There are studies that have reported no significant correlation between PFTs and duration of diseases [13]. Some studies have reported a strong negative correlation of PFTs with duration.[14,15] To summarise, our study suggests that lung function tests are impaired in diabetic persons.

Histopathological examination shows changes in the normal lung tissue in the diabetic patients. In the study by Weynand et al.,[16] it was found that alveolar epithelium, endothelium capillary, and basal laminae were thickened in lungs on electron microscopy, when compared with the controls. In addition, the thickening of basal laminae was of the same magnitude in lung and kidney. Diabetic microangiopathy might be existing in the pulmonary vascular bed. Moreover, reduced pulmonary capillary blood volume was found, favouring the evidence of microangiopathy. This could lead to redistribution of the pulmonary circulation, resulting in well ventilated areas to become under perfused.[17]. These changes results in impaired pulmonary function tests.

Limitations – Being a cross- sectional study, the progress of deterioration in the lung functions could not be analysed from the onset of diabetes mellitus. A longitudinal study design would elucidate a better relationship between the plasma glucose concentration and pulmonary function tests. A larger sample sized multicentric study would yield a better correlation. Since Assam is a place of ethnic diversity, the findings of this study cannot be extrapolated to the entire Assamese population.

Summary – The metabolic dysregulation associated with DM result in secondary pathophysiological changes in many organs of our body, including our lungs. Impaired lung functions occur because of non-enzymatic glycosylation of the collagen and elastin fibres present in the lung parenchyma. Thus, lung functions need to be checked periodically to assess the severity of impairment. The persons suffering from DM should be advised to take measures to maintain their blood glucose levels within normal range, avoid smoking, minimise their exposure to air pollution and occupational exposure to substances that may be a potential threat for chronic lung injury.

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